

PSYCHOLOGICAL METHODS BASED ON THE SCIENCE AND SUBJECT OF
GENERAL PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract. *In this study, the relevance of the problems studied by psychology in the context of globalization was explained, first of all, by the fact that each person lives in conditions of complex human relationships and information communications, and the management of human behavior is recognized as a leading factor in socio-economic development for some countries.*

Keywords: *Education, pedagogy, general psychology, psychological methods, introspection, experiment, human psyche.*

UMUMIY PSIXOLOGIYA FANI VA PREDMETI ASOSIDA PSIXOLOGIK
METODLAR

Annotatsiya. *Globalizatsiya sharoitida psixologiya o'rganadigan muammolarning dolzarbligi, avvalo, har bir shaxsning murakkab insoniy munosabatlar, axborot kommunikatsiyalari sharoitida yashayotganligi, inson xulqini boshqarish ayrim mamlakatlar uchun ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyotning yetakchi omili sifatida e'tirof etilishi bilan izohlanadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Ta'lim, pedagogika, umumiy psixologiya, psixologiya metodlari, introspektoriya, eksperiment, inson psixikasi.*

ULIWMA PSIXOLOGIYA PÁNI HÁM PREDMETI TIYKARINDA
PSIXOLOGIYALIQ METODLAR

Annotatsiya. *Bul izertlewde Globalizatsiya sharayatında psixologiya úyrenetuđın mashqalalardıń aktuallıđı, áwele, hár bir shaxstıń quramalı insaniy qatnaslar, informaciya kommunikatsiyaları sharayatında jasap atrǵanlıđı, insan xulqini basqarıw ayırım mámleketler ushın sociallıq-ekonomikalıq rawajlanıwdıń jetekshi faktori retinde tán alınıwı menen anıqlama berndi.*

Gilt sózler: Tálim, pedagogika, ulıwma psixologiya, psixologiya metodları, introspektoriya, eksperiment, insan psixikasi.

Introduction

As long as a person exists, he, based on his life experience, is responsible for himself whether he has such properties as perception, understanding the world, and distinguishing between objects and events. We hear the chirping of birds, the sound of musical instruments, human speech, the noise of a passing airplane, and see objects, trees, animals, and cars that surround us. We can distinguish their color and size. These processes are closely related to the nature of reflection in humans. When analyzing the subject of psychology, the main attention should be paid to the following. In particular, psychology and pedagogy can be included among the disciplines that consider the individual. Accordingly, pedagogy studies the development of the individual in the process of education, while psychology studies the mental processes that occur in the individual. From this we can conclude that the subject of psychology is the psyche of the individual and its psychological characteristics. The history of the emergence and development of psychology as a science is described in the scientific research of a number of scientists. The 2-volume book "What is Psychology" by the French scientist J. Godefroy states that since the ancient world, the human psyche, its soul, feelings, and behavior have been the focus of attention, the development of psychology as a science was based on the views of philosophers, the development of natural sciences, the separation of various disciplines from philosophy since the 17th century, and the approaches of Condillac, Locke, and Hume in the 18th and 19th centuries. The fact that more than 300 branches of psychology are developing as a science today indicates that psychology is becoming more and more consolidated in the system of sciences. General psychology is a special field that studies the specific aspects of all issues of psychology. Thus, modern psychology is a science that studies mental phenomena, their mechanisms, and the laws underlying them. Psychology is distinguished as a subject of study and a science. Psychology as a science is engaged in the study of the human psyche, the discovery of new laws underlying mental phenomena, the analysis of factors affecting mental life, the study of the mechanisms of various mental phenomena. Psychology as an educational subject introduces students, pupils, and specialists in various fields to the innovations and practical results discovered by the science of psychology. Psychology as an educational subject does not cover all aspects of psychology, it only covers work in certain areas. For example, it reflects the

psychological analysis and solutions to problems related to the organization and management of the educational and upbringing process in educational institutions that train teachers. Psychology is the science of mental processes and mental phenomena that actively reflect the external world in the form of sensations, perception, thinking, emotions, and other forms. For many centuries, psychology has been formed as a field of descriptive knowledge. Since ancient times, the needs of social life have required each person to study and take into account the psychological characteristics of other people, their character, behavior. Throughout life, in the process of observing the behavior of others and striving to use them in practice, a person has encountered many incomprehensible, sometimes mysterious phenomena in the spiritual world (psyche). Such phenomena were understood as the work of the soul. In their imagination, the soul is, by its very nature, immortal, invisible, odorless, divine (given by God) properties. The body is a temporary place for the soul. They believed that the soul can leave the body and return, and that the soul controls the body.

Methods of Psychology:

Introspection is the observation of one's own mental processes, the knowledge of one's own mental life without using any tools. Observation is the study of the specific features of the process without active participation in the process itself. Experiment is the study of a certain process through experiments. The experiment can be based on simulating activities under specially designed conditions or can be conducted in conditions close to normal activities. Developmental studies are studies of the specific characteristics of the same children who are observed over a period of years.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that a person turns to psychology to know himself and better understand his loved ones. This knowledge helps to see and understand the true motives of their actions.

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